

A Case of Six-Year-Old Female with Henoch-Schonlein Purpura Successfully Treated by Dexamethasone: A Case Report with Review of Literature

Author: Purushottam Adhikari

Affiliation: Gandaki Medical College, Nepal.

Submission date: 29th September, 2017; Acceptance date: 1st November, 2017

Publication date as online first: 1st November, 2017

Cite this article as: Adhikari P. A Case of Six-Year-Old Female with Henoch-Schonlein Purpura Successfully Treated by Dexamethasone: A Case Report with Review of Literature. Journal of Medical Research and Innovation. 2017;2(1):e000095. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1040294

Abstract

Henoch-Schonlein Purpura is one of the most common causes of small vessel vasculitis in children. A six-years-old female presented with abdominal pain, swelling and rashes over both the legs associated with multiple episodes of vomiting for around ten days. Stool for occult blood test was positive but there were absence of hematuria and albuminuria. The case was diagnosed as Henoch-Schlein Purpura and treated with dexamethasone for ten days. The patient was finally discharged on resolution of her symptoms. Early diagnosis and treatment favors the better outcome in cases without any renal complications.

Keywords: Henoch-Schlein Purpura, vasculitis, steroids, dexamethasone

Introduction

Henoch-Schlein Purpura, nowadays also known as IgA vasculitis is a small vessel vasculitis with IgA1-dominant immune deposits predominantly on capillaries, venules or arterioles. It often involves skin and gastrointestinal system and may also cause arthritis.(1) It is commonly seen in children and characterized by palpable purpura more commonly located in the dependent body

parts like lower extremities and buttocks, arthritis/arthralgia, bowel angina along with hematuria/proteinuria.(2) The various etiology have been suggested like varieties of pathogens, drugs, environmental exposure among which Group A beta haemolytic Streptococcus has been much studied.(3)

The natural history of disease has self limiting course in most of the cases except that those of renal complications associated with it. Symptomatic treatment with NSAIDS along with steroids will have the joint and abdominal pain relief.(4)Corticosteroids given in the early course of disease help to produce the consistently better clinical outcomes.(5) The prognosis is good, with exception of renal involvement that may need the follow up till six months or longer.(6, 7)

The exact prevalence of HSP in our settings has yet to be discovered but various studies revealed it to be one of the important cause of childhood renal disease.(8,9)

Case report

The case is reported after taking informed written consent from the patient's mother. Six years old female presented with the complaints of pain abdomen, swelling and rashes over the lower limbs and vomiting multiple episodes for ten days. Pain on the abdomen was localized around the umbilicus, sudden in onset, intermittent in nature, non radiating and relieved on lying flat on bed. She developed swelling of both legs subsequently a day after abdominal pain along with appearance of rashes starting from feet and progressing to thigh and buttocks. She also developed vomiting around three to five episodes for last five days. The vomiting was non projectile, non blood stained and it contained food particles whatever eaten.

On examination, general condition of patient was fair and vitals were stable. Abdomen was soft and non tender. Mild bilateral non pitting edema was present over both legs. There was presence of non-tender, non-blanching, purpuric rashes over the both lower limbs extending upto buttocks.

Laboratory tests showed leucocytosis with WBC: 12,000/mm³; Neutrophils: 8,800/mm³; Lymphocyte: 3,200/mm³; Platelets: 4,22,000/mm³; Hemoglobin: 14 gm/dl; ESR: 12 mm/1sthour; Serum Urea: 33 mg/dl; Serum Creatinine: 0.6 mg/dl; Sodium: 139 mmol/litre; Potassium: 4.6 mmol/litre; CRP: 0.92 mg/litre; Urinalysis: no hematuria or proteinuria; Stool analysis: Occult blood test positive. Plain X-ray abdomen and Ultrasound abdomen/pelvis revealed normal scan.

Diagnosis of Henoch-Schlein Purpura was made in accordance with American College of Rheumatology and European League Against Rheumatism (EuLAR) and Pediatric Rheumatology Society (PReS) criteria.(8, 9)

She was treated with Dexamethasone 0.14 mg/kg/dose four times a day intravenously for five days and then tapered to three times a day for three days and two times a day for next two days.

Purpura and bilateral swelling of legs in first week and its recovery progress after treatment has started in second and third week is shown in figure 1, 2, and 3.

Figure 1. Purpura and swelling of bilateral lower limbs in first week

Figure 2. Progress of purpura in second week after the admission of patient in hospital

Figure 3. Third week before the discharge from hospital

Discussion

Henoch-Schlein Purpura (HSP) was first described by William Heberden in 1801. Later Schlein recognized the association between purpura and arthritis whereas Henoch reported a case that also included gastrointestinal symptoms along with renal involvement.⁽¹⁰⁾ HSP is the most common vasculitis of the children. Half among the all cases occur before the age of five and males are affected twice as common as females.⁽¹¹⁾ Though the case reported here is of six years old female.

The exact etiology and pathogenesis of HSP is yet to be determined. Seasonal variation has been related with high prevalence from autumn and winter.⁽²⁾ The case described here has been diagnosed in Spring. It has been proposed that various triggers like bacterial and viral infections, vaccinations, drugs and autoimmune mechanisms results in formation of antigen and antibody complex. The deposition of the formed immune complex in the small vessels activates the alternate compliment pathway, neutrophil aggregation which results in inflammation and vasculitis.⁽¹²⁾ Among all, the preceding infection of β -haemolytic Streptococcus has been one of the most studied and positive throat cultures as well as increased titers of anti-streptolysin O has been found in some.⁽³⁾ The evidence of prior infection has not been recorded in our case.

The patient generally presents with the classic tetrad of rashes, polyarthralgia, abdominal pain, and renal disease. The non blanching rashes clinically appear as palpable purpura on lower legs and arms.(11) Joint involvement is characterized by the pain and swelling of the joints affecting the knees and ankles. Abdominal pain followed by vomiting and intestinal bleeding are the dominant features involving the gastrointestinal system. Microscopic hematuria and albuminuria are the prominent renal findings.(5, 13)

Our case had the symptoms of rashes over the both lower legs, pain abdomen and vomiting. Joint involvement was absent. Significant laboratory finding was occult blood test positive in stool. There were no hematuria and albuminuria.

The diagnosis of HSP is made by American College of Rheumatology – 1990 criteria and EuLAR/PReS – 2006 criteria.(8, 9)

Table 1.American College of Rheumatology – 1990 criteria for the diagnosis of HSP

Criterion	Definition
Palpable purpura	Slightly raised “palpable” hemorrhagic skin lesions, not related to thrombocytopenia
Age <20 at disease onset	Patient 20 years or younger at onset of first symptoms
Bowel angina	Diffuse abdominal pain, worse after meals, or the diagnosis of bowel ischemia, usually including bloody diarrhea
Wall granulocytes on biopsy	Histologic changes showing granulocytes in the walls of arterioles or venules

The patient is said to have HSP if at least two of the four above criteria is present. In our case there were presence of palpable purpura, age <20 at disease onset and bowel angina and thus diagnosed as HSP.

Table 2. EuLAR/PReS – 2006 criteria

Criteria	Definition
Mandatory criteria	Palpable purpura
Additional criteria	Diffuse abdominal pain
	Any biopsy showing predominant IgA deposition
	Arthritis or arthralgia
	Renal involvement (any haematuria and/or proteinuria)

The patient is said to have HSP if mandatory criteria is present along with at least one of the additional criteria. Our case fulfilled the mandatory criteria along with diffuse abdominal pain as the additional criteria.

There is predominantly spontaneous resolution of all symptoms except that of the renal disease in majority of the cases. Steroids are more often used for the relief of abdominal pain, joint pain and skin disease. Alternatively, Methotrexate and Dapsone has been quite effective steroid sparing agent for the chronic abdominal pain and skin involvement.(4)The role of corticosteroids in preventing the long term outcome of renal complications is controversial.A meta-analysis in the Medline database and the Cochrane Controlled Trials Register based on a comprehensive review of the literature by Weiss et al. stated that early treatment with corticosteroid significantly reduced the odds of developing persistent renal disease along with surgical intervention and recurrence.(5) In contrary, other trials and updates in literature had mentioned that there is no long term renal protective outcome with the early treatment with prednisolone.(14, 15)

Generally prednisolone is the commonly used steroids used for the treatment of HSP. Though in our case we used dexamethasone, there is no evidence in literature to prove the superiority of one over another. Several cases and studies have been reported resulting in better outcomes on treatment with dexamethasone.(16, 17)

Renal involvement has high morbidity and increases the mortality, otherwise the disease has better prognosis.(7) A systematic review by Narchi H stated that even if urinalysis is normal at the presentation, follow up urine testing should be continued for six months as 97 % children who will develop abnormal urine findings would appear by that time.(6)

Rarely few cases of complicated HSP as intussusceptions, gastrointestinal bleeding, cardiac involvement have been reported.(16, 18, 19)

Conclusion

Henoch-Schlein Purpura being the most common vasculitis of the children and its classic presentation of palpable purpura, arthritis, abdominal involvement and renal features makes the diagnosis easier. Early initiation of treatment with steroids will help in symptomatic relief and somehow bring a positive outcome. Renal disease may need the long term follow up; otherwise the diseases has favourable prognosis.

Acknowledgement

Author would like to acknowledge the patient's mother for providing consent for the case report. Also authors would like to thank to the faculties of Department of Pediatrics, Gandaki Medical College for their support, guidance and suggestion during the course of study.

References

1. Jennette JC, Falk RJ, Bacon PA, Basu N, Cid MC, Ferrario F, et al. 2012 revised International Chapel Hill Consensus Conference Nomenclature of Vasculitides. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2013;65(1):1-11. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23045170> DOI: [10.1002/art.37715](https://doi.org/10.1002/art.37715)
2. Yang YH, Yu HH, Chiang BL. The diagnosis and classification of Henoch-Schonlein purpura: an updated review. *Autoimmunity reviews.* 2014;13(4-5):355-8. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24424188> DOI: [10.1016/j.autrev.2014.01.031](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autrev.2014.01.031)
3. Saulsbury FT. Clinical update: Henoch-Schonlein purpura. *Lancet (London, England).* 2007;369(9566):976-8. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/17382810> DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(07\)60474-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(07)60474-7)
4. Tizard EJ, Hamilton-Ayres MJ. Henoch Schonlein purpura. *Archives of disease in childhood Education and practice edition.* 2008;93(1):1-8. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18208978> DOI: [10.1136/adc.2004.066035](https://doi.org/10.1136/adc.2004.066035)
5. Weiss PF, Feinstein JA, Luan X, Burnham JM, Feudtner C. Effects of corticosteroid on Henoch-Schonlein purpura: a systematic review. *Pediatrics.* 2007;120(5):1079-87. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/17974746> DOI: [10.1542/peds.2007-0667](https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2007-0667)
6. Narchi H. Risk of long term renal impairment and duration of follow up recommended for Henoch-Schönlein purpura with normal or minimal urinary findings: a systematic review. *Archives of Disease in Childhood.* 2005;90(9):916-20. PMID:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1720564/> DOI: [10.1136/adc.2005.074641](https://doi.org/10.1136/adc.2005.074641)

7. Calvo-Rio V, Loricera J, Mata C, Martin L, Ortiz-Sanjuan F, Alvarez L, et al. Henoch-Schonlein purpura in northern Spain: clinical spectrum of the disease in 417 patients from a single center. *Medicine*. 2014;93(2):106-13. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24646467> DOI: [10.1097/MD.0000000000000019](https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.0000000000000019)
8. Bhatta NK, Shrestha P, Budhathoki S, Kalakheti BK, Poudel P, Sinha A, et al. Profile of renal diseases in Nepalese children. *Kathmandu Univ Med J (KUMJ)*. 2008;6(2):191-4. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18769085>
9. Shah G. Clinical profile and pattern of Henoch-Schönlein purpura in children. *Journal of Patan Academy of Health Sciences*. 2015;2(1):17-21 URL: <http://jpahs.edu.np/index.php/JPAHS/article/view/45>
10. Mills JA, Michel BA, Bloch DA, Calabrese LH, Hunder GG, Arend WP, et al. The American College of Rheumatology 1990 criteria for the classification of Henoch-Schonlein purpura. *Arthritis Rheum*. 1990;33(8):1114-21. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/2202310> DOI: [10.1002/art.1780330809](https://doi.org/10.1002/art.1780330809)
11. Ozen S, Ruperto N, Dillon MJ, Bagga A, Barron K, Davin JC, et al. EULAR/PreS endorsed consensus criteria for the classification of childhood vasculitides. *Annals of the rheumatic diseases*. 2006;65(7):936-41. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/16322081> DOI: [10.1136/ard.2005.046300](https://doi.org/10.1136/ard.2005.046300)
12. Ballinger S. Henoch-Schonlein purpura. Current opinion in rheumatology. 2003;15(5):591-4. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12960486> URL: http://journals.lww.com/co-rheumatology/Abstract/2003/09000/Henoch_Schonlein_purpura.12.aspx
13. Roberts PF, Waller TA, Brinker TM, Riffe IZ, Sayre JW, Bratton RL. Henoch-Schonlein purpura: a review article. *Southern medical journal*. 2007;100(8):821-4. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/17713309> DOI: [10.1097/SMJ.0b013e3180f62d0f](https://doi.org/10.1097/SMJ.0b013e3180f62d0f)
14. Sohagia AB, Gunturu SG, Tong TR, Hertan HI. Henoch-schonlein purpura-a case report and review of the literature. *Gastroenterol Res Pract*. 2010;2010:597648. URL: <https://www.hindawi.com/journals/grp/2010/597648/> DOI: [10.1155/2010/597648](https://doi.org/10.1155/2010/597648)
15. Chen O, Zhu XB, Ren P, Wang YB, Sun RP, Wei DE. Henoch Schonlein Purpura in children: clinical analysis of 120 cases. *African Health Sciences*. 2013;13(1):94-9. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3645106/> DOI: [10.4314/ahs.v13i1.26](https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v13i1.26)
16. Dudley J, Smith G, Llewelyn-Edwards A, Bayliss K, Pike K, Tizard J. Randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial to determine whether steroids reduce the incidence and severity of

nephropathy in Henoch-Schonlein Purpura (HSP). Arch Dis Child. 2013;98(10):756-63. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23845696> DOI: [10.1136/archdischild-2013-303642](https://doi.org/10.1136/archdischild-2013-303642)

17. Bluman J, Goldman RD. Henoch-Schönlein purpura in children: Limited benefit of corticosteroids. Canadian Family Physician. 2014;60(11):1007-10. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4229160/> URL: <http://www.cfp.ca/content/60/11/1007>

18. Yamazaki T, Akimoto T, Iwazu Y, Sugase T, Takeshima E, Numata A, et al. Henoch-Schonlein purpura complicated with severe gastrointestinal bleeding. CEN Case Rep. 2015;4(1):106-11. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5411628> DOI: [10.1007/s13730-014-0148-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13730-014-0148-8)

19. Lutz HH, Ackermann T, Krombach GA, Grone HJ, Rauen T, Floege J, et al. Henoch-Schonlein purpura complicated by cardiac involvement: case report and review of the literature. Am J Kidney Dis. 2009;54(5):e9-15. PMID: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19535191> DOI: [10.1053/j.ajkd.2009.04.017](https://doi.org/10.1053/j.ajkd.2009.04.017)